

DIGITAL EDUCATION AND ITS DISTINGUISHING FEATURES

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Annotation: There is conclusive evidence that digital devices, tools, and resources, when used effectively, can increase the speed and depth of science and mathematics learning for learners at the primary and secondary levels. There is suggestive evidence that the same can be said for some aspects of literacy, particularly writing and comprehension. Digital technology appears to be an appropriate vehicle for improving basic literacy and numeracy skills, especially in primary education. While there are benefits to the use of digital learning, the magnitude of the effects is generally similar to other educational interventions that are effective in raising achievement. The extent of the effect may also be tempered by teachers' level of competence in effective digital learning tools and resources to improve learning outcomes. More effective use of digital education to raise achievement requires that teachers have the ability to identify how digital tools and resources can be used to achieve learning outcomes and adapt their approaches, as well as knowledge and understand technology. In this article, all features will be analyzed.

Keywords: TEL, digital education, progressive instruction, smart classrooms, thinking out of box.

ЦИФРОВОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ И ЕГО ОСОБЕННОСТИ

Аннотация: Имеются убедительные доказательства того, что цифровые устройства, инструменты и ресурсы при эффективном использовании могут повысить скорость и глубину изучения естественных наук и математики для учащихся начальной и средней школы. Имеются убедительные доказательства того, что то же самое можно сказать и о некоторых аспектах грамотности, особенно о письме и понимании. Цифровые технологии представляются подходящим средством для улучшения базовых навыков грамотности и счета, особенно в начальном образовании. Хотя использование цифрового обучения имеет свои преимущества, масштабы эффектов в целом аналогичны другим образовательным вмешательствам, которые эффективны для повышения успеваемости. Масштабы эффекта также могут быть ограничены уровнем компетентности учителей в использовании эффективных инструментов и ресурсов цифрового обучения для улучшения результатов обучения. Более эффективное использование цифрового образования для повышения успеваемости требует, чтобы учителя имели возможность определять, как можно использовать цифровые инструменты и ресурсы для достижения результатов обучения, и адаптировать свои подходы, а также признавать и понимать технологии. В этой статье будут проанализированы все особенности.

Ключевые слова: TEL, цифровое образование, прогрессивное обучение, умные классы, нестандартное мышление.

Introduction.

What is digital education? Digital learning is the novel use of current technologies and digitised tools to facilitate the progress of instruction and learning. It is often also referred to as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL), e-learning or digital learning. Literacy is the pathway to education through technology and digital devices. A digital transformation of a country is underway and the digital evolution of the economy and society is only possible through digital

education. The notion of digital training is not a new one and has existed in different form for many years, yet when pandemic COVID-19 suspended residential education, its significance has multiplied. Most of the institutions have been using the digital learning as a problem solver, while traditional learning in the classrooms has for some time been sidelined due to the pandemic prevailing nowadays. One of the fundamental components of the United Nations' sustainable development 2030 agenda is quality education. It aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all. Digital technologies have emerged as an essential tool to achieve this goal. These technologies are simple to detect emissions sources, prevent additional damage through improved energy efficiency and lower-carbon alternatives to fossil fuels, and even remove surplus greenhouse gases from the environment. Digital technologies strive to decrease or eliminate pollution and waste while increasing production and efficiency. These technologies have shown a powerful impact on the education system. The recent COVID-19 Pandemic has further institutionalised the applications of digital technologies in education. These digital technologies have made a paradigm shift in the entire education system. It is not only a knowledge provider but also a co-creator of information, a mentor, and an assessor. Technological improvements in education have made life easier for students. Instead of using pen and paper, students nowadays use various software and tools to create presentations and projects. When compared to a stack of notebooks, an iPad is relatively light. When opposed to a weighty book, surfing an E-book is easier. These methods aid in increasing interest in research.[1] The digital learning is seen as an effective alternative to the traditional process of learning by chalk and talk. Learning is no more limited to textbooks and textbooks and is no longer limited to the classroom. Learning is no more confined to the textbook and the classroom; it has evolved into a fusion of technologies, innovative instruction and digital content. The web has also become much more affordable and easily accessible, and this will result in a larger fusion between digital and conventional methods of learning. The government is actively engaged in taking important policy measures that will promote the growth of digital learning market in India. There are efforts to raise standards of digital infrastructures in India to make it easier to adopt the innovative educational instruments. People ask me, "What is driving technology? Is it large companies, venture capital, cat memes . . . ?" The answer: children. Generation Z and Generation Alpha are the children of Millennials and represent the most digital and diverse generations in history. Fifty percent of children under 15 are from minority households, and the United States will be multicultural majority by 2050. However, it is a problem that today's family entertainment is disconnected from where we are as a country: 50% of leading characters on children's television are White, 27% are animals, 10% are Black, 7% are Asian, 5% are Latinx, and 1% are Native American. Animals are better represented than some of the key ethnic demographics among today's children. Those same demographics tend to be underserved by education.[2]

Benefits of the digital training gadget:

Individualized approach to studying: the main disadvantage of the conventional education system is that many college students enjoy a loss of hobby after they cannot capture up with the relaxation of the elegance. Brand new virtual format permits instructors to individualize learning fabric according to the speed and ability of every pupil. The impact of educational programmes will increase with the digitalization of education.

Students turn out to be Smarter: when exposed to new learning gear and generation college students develop powerful self-directed gaining knowledge of skills. The virtual training device allows students to analyze what they need to recognise on the way to search and make use of on

line resources. It plays a huge function in magnifying their efficiency, studying ability, and productivity.

Unlimited statistics: the world of the net is tremendous and loaded with facts, maximum of that's freely available. The emergence of digital education has made it viable for students to explore and use this treasure of know-how. In advance, students could depend upon limited sources of records, however now thanks to the developing popularity of the digital education system, unavailability of the specified records is not a barrier in searching for know-how. There are undoubtedly several benefits associated with digital education, but we cannot overlook the drawbacks of this sudden change in the education system. Life for today's students is becoming increasingly virtual. The students, from primary school kids to college graduates, are experiencing and displaying a change in communication methods. For example; they would rather receive or send a text instead of a phone call or a face-to-face meeting. We see the youth spending more time on digital platforms and endorsing technology that further digitalises their life, which reduces offline personal interaction in their daily lives. People are increasingly concerned that digital devices will leave their kids unable to adequately interact with the real world around them. The drastic increase in the number of hours children spend on screens has only aggravated the fear of social and cognitive impairment in children.[3]

Smart lecture rooms: The chalk and speak method is now a component of the past, and instructors are utilising greater tech-savvy methods to help college students understand that learning may be revolutionary and fun. The current-day school rooms are geared up with a tv or a projector which makes it is simple to shift from a regular school room consultation to an interactive

digital consultation. This could make college students pay extra interest as they are appreciably familiar with the digital world.

The benefits and drawbacks of digitalisation in education can be discussed ad nauseam. But one thing is certain that the future is digital. Digitalisation as a process affects not only education, but nearly every aspect of life. Hence, it is imperative that students learn to use this convenience the way it was intended to be used as a tool to improve life, and not one to replace crucial aspects of it.[4]

Digitised learning is the ingenious use of digitised techniques and instruments in teaching and learning, which is frequently referred to as Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) or digital learning. Teachers and students must be able to learn at the right time, at chosen locations, at different times and at the wrong pace, and at the right time. Digitised education is replacing traditional learning procedures more and more every day. If you are wondering what is digital learning system and what are the benefits for the students, here we give details of what digital learning is and what are the advantages for the students. Exploring the use of digitisation gives educators the chance to develop exciting learning experiences within the subjects they teach, which can take the form of combined or entirely on-line courses and curricula. There is more to offering digital learning than just providing students with a laptop. Digital learning requires a combination of technology, teaching and digital content. Incorporating digital teaching into the classroom can depend on the use of tablets rather than paper, to the use of complex programmes and hardware as against a simple pen. Digitised Learning has now become a commonplace in today's world. With the advent of the internet, the opportunities for the modern world have become vast. Digital education has transformed the old process of learning in the classroom with chalk and blackboards. It made learning portable, interactive and fun, encouraging students to take an interested and engaged interest in digital learning. Most of the schools and learning institutions are embracing this technology as a solution, while the traditional education system has been suspended for some time due to the prevailing conditions at present. It is therefore very much important for us to recognise some of the major benefits of the digital learning environment.

Digitally up to date: In a world this is ever-evolving in terms of era, practices and information can effortlessly emerge as old, as there is usually some thing new transpiring. Equipping college students with updated information and different problem-related subjects is now not a matter of desire, but a mandatory method. College students spend most of their time on their phones and laptops, so that they ought to be sound era-smart. UNICEF is on the ground in over 190 countries and territories, working across borders and barriers to reach children with the learning opportunities they need to succeed. Non-political and impartial, we're never neutral when it comes to protecting a child's right to education. But we can't do it alone. We team up with communities, governments and businesses to:

❖ **Make digital learning equitable and safe**

We ensure our solutions run effectively offline or with limited connectivity, function on low-cost devices, are accessible and inclusive for children with disabilities, and translate into local languages and cultural contexts. Our solutions also adhere to global best practices for online safety and data protection.

❖ **Improve the quality of digital learning**

We use evidence to design and implement digital learning programmes that are flexible and personalized, adapting to each learner's level. Our focus is on strengthening literacy and numeracy, plus digital skills, so children build a foundation for lifelong learning.

❖ **Integrate digital learning across settings**

We build the capacity of teachers and administrators to apply digital pedagogies and technologies, and help caregivers and communities support high-tech and low-tech digital learning. Our solutions reach refugee centres, homes and schools, even in emergency contexts.[5]

High Engagement studying: The conventional schooling device presents limited scope for engagement as its forces at work encompass constrained elements like textbooks, a trainer, and hand-written notes, whereas the digitized training device gives a wide range of picks to study from. The limitless availability of resources makes each session extremely revolutionary and attractive. The interactive and recreation-based totally gaining knowledge of periods benefit better engagement from students.

Ease of Sharing: The traditional training system might heavily depend on college students retaining thick notebooks of hand-written notes containing statistics provided by means of teachers within the classroom or acquired via substantial studies in the library, but the modern digital education gadget changes the whole lot. Now preserving and sharing records is only a click away which saves students quite a few time and physical exertions.

Responsibility in students: The virtual schooling gadget includes actual-time evaluation and device-generated performance reviews which increases the transparency of assessment. It enables college students to analyze their overall performance and provide you with required answers on their very own. The digital education machine brings students out of their shells and makes them impartial thinkers who recognize what to have a look at, when to observe and a way to have a look at. They no longer remain depending on their instructors and dad and mom to spoon-feed them with information.

To alternate not best what we research, however additionally how we learn is the want of the hour. The involvement of virtual systems, the digital international, augmented fact, online libraries, and webinars are the brand new chalk and board of our training machine whilst serps have turn out to be the brand new library.

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